

EMPOWERMENT AND ORGANIZATIONAL BEHAVIORS: A STUDY OF PRIVATE SCHOOL TEACHERS IN CABUYAO, LAGUNA

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10983699>

ABSTRACT

This research investigated the relationship between teacher empowerment and organizational behavior in 30 private school teachers from thirteen schools in Brgy. Mamatid, Cabuyao, Laguna. A review of relevant literature provided the theoretical foundation for the study. Employing a descriptive design, questionnaires were used to collect data. The findings revealed that the teachers felt empowered, with positive views on their ability to manage personal and professional development. Additionally, they demonstrated high levels of organizational commitment, particularly moral commitment. They consistently exhibited all dimensions of organizational citizenship behavior, with kindness being the least frequent. Overall, the teachers displayed high levels of positive organizational behaviors within their schools. The statistical analysis using regression confirmed a significant influence of teacher empowerment on their organizational behavior. These findings hold implications for the management of teacher education institutions. The results of the regression analysis indicate significant relationships between predictor variables (teacher empowerment, organizational commitment, and professional commitment) and the criterion variable of teachers' organizational behaviors. Specifically, teacher empowerment demonstrates a Beta coefficient of 0.264, organizational commitment shows a coefficient of 0.078, and professional commitment exhibits the highest coefficient at 0.65. These coefficients are associated with p-values below the 0.05 alpha threshold, indicating statistical significance. Furthermore, the collective predictive power of these variables is underscored by an F value of 39.087 with a corresponding significant value of 0.000, well below the 0.05 alpha threshold. This finding suggests that the combined influence of the predictor variables explains a statistically significant proportion of the variance in teachers' organizational behaviors. In light of these results, it is evident that teacher empowerment significantly influences teachers' organizational behaviors. Therefore, the null hypothesis, which posits no significant influence of empowerment on organizational behaviors, is rejected based on the analysis outcomes and associated probabilities.

Keywords: *Teacher Empowerment, Organizational Behavior, Private School Teachers, Organizational Commitment*

INTRODUCTION

Every organization needs Human Resource Management because employees are valuable assets. They bring with them their knowledge and experience, gained through their work and learning (Imam & Shafique, 2018). Human capital is the heart of any successful project. Companies increasingly value employees who go the extra mile, beyond just their job duties. By equipping them with the right resources, organizations empower their workforce to reach their peak potential. This focus on employee effectiveness and efficiency benefits everyone involved. People are the engines of innovation and creativity, driving success for both employers and them.

Teachers are key to a school's achievements, especially when it comes to providing a good education for their students, who are the school's main focus. In fact, teachers are often seen as nation builders because a country's success in any field relies on the knowledge and skills that teachers give to their students (Duncan & Sunkey, 2019). Schools can't function without teachers. Their knowledge, creativity, and ongoing learning are crucial to the system's success (Cheasakul & Varma, 2018). Because of this, empowering teachers is a smart move for any school. "Teacher empowerment" is a common term in education discussions, and research shows it can significantly boost teachers' "organizational citizenship behavior" (OCB) (Mesbahi, 2017). This basically means teachers going above and beyond their job descriptions to help the school improve. Since OCB helps schools thrive, it makes sense for any institution to empower its teachers and encourage them to freely contribute their time and energy.

Effective teachers go beyond simply completing tasks. They actively create a positive learning environment - meaningful, student-centered, creative, adaptable, and encouraging open communication. This extends to their role as role models, striving to make the school itself more effective and efficient. Their dedication goes above and beyond expectations, driven by a spirit of service to the organization. To further empower teachers, school leaders should foster a culture of decision-making, providing necessary resources and information for teachers to take ownership of their choices and implement them. However, some teachers may resist such changes.

Since empowered teachers tend to demonstrate positive behaviors within the school (Tindowen, 2019), this research investigates how teacher empowerment impacts the way teachers working in Brgy. Mamatid, Cabuyao Laguna, behave within their school organization.

Research Questions

The general problem of the study was: How may empowering teachers influence organizational behaviors?

Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. How may the empowerment of the respondents be described in terms of:
 - 1.1 Trust;
 - 1.2 Professional Development;
 - 1.3 Status; and
 - 1.4 Cooperation?
 2. How may the organizational behaviors of the respondents be described in terms of:
 - 2.1 Organizational commitment;
 - 2.2 Professional commitment; and
 - 2.3. Organizational citizenship behaviors
 3. Does empowerment significantly influence teachers' organizational behaviors?
 4. What management implications maybe drawn from the findings of the study?
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METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The quantitative research approach was employed in this study to analyze the influence of empowerment on teachers' organizational behaviors in thirteen private schools in Brgy, Mamatid Cabuyao Laguna . Bhandari (2020) defines quantitative research as collecting and analyzing numerical data in order to identify patterns and averages, create predictions, examine causal connections, and generalize conclusions to broader populations.

The researcher conducted a survey for this study using an adapted questionnaire was used as a measurement instrument. The respondents were required to respond to all items on the questionnaire, providing their perspectives on the influence of empowerment on the organizational behaviors of teachers.

A set of standardized questionnaires on the profile characteristics, empowerment, organizational commitment, professional commitment, and teachers' organizational behaviors was used as primary data-gathering tools.

Research Locale

The study will be conducted Brgy, Mamatid Cabuya Laguna consist of thirteen bdifferent private schools.

Population and Sample

The research population for this study consisted of 30 private school teachers from Brgy, Mamatid, Cabuyao Laguna for the S.Y. 2022-2023, who answered the survey questionnaire selected through convenience sampling and fishbowl sampling. The respondents were selected to come up with sufficient data to serve as background information that might be the answer to the problem. Respondents were given survey

questionnaires from which they selected the best response evaluating the influence of empowerment on teachers' organizational behaviors.

Research Instrument

This research relied heavily on the questionnaire as the significant instrument and primary source of gathering data. The study used a set of questionnaires that were answered by the respondents that revealed the influence of empowerment on teachers' organizational behaviors. The researcher asked permission from the authors to use the questionnaire with some revisions to fit the nature of the respondents.

In this study, four data collection instruments were utilized to gather relevant information. Section A employed the "Teacher Empowerment Scale," designed by Özkan Hıdıroğlu and Tanrıoğen (2022), to assess teacher empowerment. Section B incorporated the "Organizational Commitment Scale," Teachers' Professional Commitment Scale," is adapted on the study of Ergen and Kanadili (2017), to gauge organizational commitment across 15 items structured into three dimensions.

Lastly, section D employed the "Organizational Citizenship Behaviors Scale," adapted to the of Polat (2019) from the original work by Podsakoff et al. (1990), to measure organizational citizenship behavior.

Under each statement is a 5-point scale providing alternatives to identify the degree of agreement or disagreement each respondent will have on every statement. The respondents were asked to pick one of the choices strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, and strongly disagree.

Validation of Questionnaire

To make sure that the questionnaire is valid and reliable, the draft of the questionnaire was submitted to the thesis adviser to address some comments and recommendation before it was pretested for certain validation among the respondents. The research acquired Cronbach-Alpha result of (0.9457) of the questionnaires administered for validation. It denotes that the questionnaire is valid and reliable.

Data Gathering Procedure

The mode of data gathering was the questionnaire method. Each respondent was given a well-structured, well-instructed, and standardized set of questions to describe their profile characteristics quantitatively, empowerment, organizational commitment, professional commitment, and organizational behaviors.

The researcher collected the questionnaires from the respondents. The researcher checked if all the items are answered religiously for the conduct of the study.

Statistical Treatment of the Data

The data collected underwent tabulation and processing using the Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS). The findings were then presented utilizing appropriate tables and figures. Respondents' profile characteristics were obtained through a simple method where respondents indicated their personal information by marking, shading, or checking corresponding circles on a questionnaire.

Meanwhile, to analyze and assess the impact of empowerment on teachers' organizational behaviors, regression analysis was employed by the researcher. The study utilized weighted mean calculation, aggregating scores from the questionnaire checklist. The outcomes were subsequently shared with experts from Meycauayan College, as well as with the advisor and critics for evaluation and feedback.

Scale	Range	Descriptive Evaluation	Agreement Degree
5	4.21-5.0	Strongly Agree	Very High
4	3.41-4.20	Agree	High
3	2.61-3.40	Neutral	Neutral
2	1.81-2.60	Disagree	Low
1	1.00-1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

This illustrates the utilization of a descriptive scale to assess mean scores related to empowerment, organizational commitment, and teachers' organizational behaviors, as well as the impact of empowerment on teachers' organizational behaviors. The scale categorizes mean scores into distinct interpretations: a score ranging from 1.00 to 1.80 signifies strong disagreement, a score between 1.81 and 2.60 denotes disagreement, a score from 2.61 to 3.40 indicates neutrality, a score between 3.41 and 4.20 represents agreement, and a score falling within the range of 4.21 to 5.0 is interpreted as strong agreement.

RESULTS

When discussing empowerment and its conceptualization, it's important to recognize the scholarly literature on the subject. According to Kabeer (2019), empowerment involves "the expansion in people's ability to make strategic life choices in a context where this ability was previously denied to them" (p. 437). This definition underscores the significance of agency and the removal of structural barriers that limit individuals' capacity to control their lives and participate fully in society. In essence, empowerment encompasses both individual capabilities and broader societal transformations aimed at redistributing power and fostering inclusive development (Kabeer, 2019).

Table 2. *Empowerment in Terms of Trust*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1. I feel that my administrators value me as a teacher.	4.73	Strongly Agree
2. My administrators treat me empathically.	4.62	Strongly Agree
3. Our administrators do not let our time go to waste with unnecessary works.	4.63	Strongly Agree
4. My administrators give me the opportunity to say my thoughts.	4.65	Strongly Agree
5. I think I have a profession with high social status.	4.60	Strongly Agree
6. The teaching profession provides me with the social status I desire in my environment.	4.65	Strongly Agree
7. Teaching makes it possible for me to deal with many cultural issues.	4.63	Strongly Agree
8. The attitudes of people around me towards teachers make me strong.	4.69	Strongly Agree
9. The teaching profession gives me confidence.	4.79	Strongly Agree
10. The teaching profession gives me dignity.	4.81	Strongly Agree
11. Other teachers at our school appreciate my work.	4.65	Strongly Agree
12. I have a chance to cooperate with other teachers at my school.	4.78	Strongly Agree
Average	4.69	Strongly Agree

Table 2 presents teacher empowerment in terms of trust. As shown in the table, the overall mean was 4.69 with a verbal interpretation of strongly agree or very high. This implies that the respondents strongly agreed with the views cited along with teacher empowerment in terms of trust.

All of the respondents rated strongly agreed with all the indicators on the following statements: I feel that my administrators value me as a teacher with 4.73; My administrators treat me empathically with 4.62; Our administrators do not let our time go to waste with unnecessary work with 4.63; My administrators give me the opportunity to say my thoughts with 4.65; I think I have a profession with high social status with 4.60; The teaching profession provides me with the social status I desire in my environment with 4.65; Teaching makes it possible for me to deal with many cultural issues with 4.63; The attitudes of people around me towards teachers make me strong with 4.69; The teaching profession gives me confidence with 4.79; The teaching profession gives me dignity with 4.81; Other teachers at our school appreciate my work with 4.65; and lastly, I have a chance to cooperate with other teachers at my school with 4.78.

Table 3. *Empowerment in Terms of Professional Development*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1. Participation in seminars/conferences of important people in my profession is not prevented by the school administration.	4.70	Strongly Agree
2. It is not prevented by the school administration to participate in any kind of training related to my branch.	4.72	Strongly Agree
3. Attending personal development courses (drama, diction, personal development, effective communication, etc.) is supported by the school management.	4.69	Strongly Agree
4. I have the chance to receive trainings about immigrant or problem students by the school administration.	3.96	Agree
5. It is supported by the school administration to receive training on educational technology.	4.31	Agree
6. I have the chance to receive trainings on new teaching methods and techniques by the school administration.	4.76	Strongly Agree
7. I have the chance to participate in in-service trainings frequently and regularly by the school administration.	4.76	Strongly Agree
8. It is supported by the school administration to participate in scientific training in my environment.	4.21	Agree
9. It is supported by the school administration to receive trainings on classroom management.	4.79	Strongly Agree
10. I have chance to participate in training (legislative training) where my Powers and rights are taught.	4.14	Agree
11. The school administration provides me with an environment to attend the courses and trainings I need.	4.27	Agree
Average	4.46	Agree

Table 3 presents the empowerment of teachers in terms of professional development. As shown in the table, the overall mean was 4.46 with a verbal interpretation of agree. This implies that the respondents had a high level of empowerment in terms of professional development.

Most of the respondents rated strongly agreed with most of the indicators with the following statements: Participation in seminars/conferences of important people in my profession is not prevented by the school administration with 4.70; It is not prevented by the school administration to participate in any kind of training related to my branch with 4.72; Attending personal development courses (drama, diction, personal development, effective communication, etc.) is supported by the school management with 4.69; I have

the chance to receive trainings on new teaching methods and techniques by the school administration with 4.76; I have the chance to participate in in-service trainings frequently and regularly by the school administration with 4.76; and lastly, It is supported by the school administration to receive trainings on classroom management with 4.79.

On the other hand, 4. I have the chance to receive trainings about immigrant or problem students by the school administration with 3.96; It is supported by the school administration to receive training on educational technology with 4.31; 8. It is supported by the school administration to participate in scientific training in my environment with 4.21; I have chance to participate in training (legislative training) where my Powers and rights are taught with 4.14; and The school administration provides me with an environment to attend the courses and trainings I need with 4.27 which all indicated agree as a verbal description.

Table 4. *Empowerment in Terms of Status*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1. My administrators have an understanding towards me.	4.71	Strongly Agree
2. My administrators are supportive of my profession.	4.70	Strongly Agree
3. My administrators behave fairly within the school.	4.72	Strongly Agree
4. I have a healthy dialogue with my administrators.	4.71	Strongly Agree
5. My administrators contact me individually when there is a problem.	4.71	Strongly Agree
6. My administrators respect me.	4.75	Strongly Agree
7. My administrators apply school rules in the same way to everyone.	4.72	Strongly Agree
8. I feel free while carrying out my duties.	4.73	Strongly Agree
Average	4.72	Strongly Agree

Table 4 shows that teachers perceive their level of empowerment in terms of their status as very high or strongly agree with 4.72. All of the respondents rated strongly agreed with all the indicators on the following statements: My administrators have an understanding towards me; My administrators are supportive of my profession; My administrators behave fairly within the school; I have a healthy dialogue with my administrators; My administrators contact me individually when there is a problem; My administrators respect me; My administrators apply school rules in the same way to everyone; and I feel free while carrying out my duties with 4.71, 4.70, 4.72, 4.71, 4.71, 4.75, 4.72, and 4.73 of mean scores, respectively.

Table 5. *Empowerment in Terms of Cooperation*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1. People around me respect the teaching profession.	4.76	Strongly Agree
2. Teachers are well accepted by people in this area.	4.76	Strongly Agree
3. The teachers in our school cooperate with each other in line with their Professional goals.	4.77	Strongly Agree
4. Our school has a teaching staff to work with pleasure.	4.73	Strongly Agree
5. The cooperation of the teachers in our school makes me feel safe.	4.74	Strongly Agree
6. I think that the teacher I work with has Professional ethics.	4.74	Strongly Agree
Average	4.75	Strongly Agree

The data presented in Table 5 reveals the level of empowerment of the teachers in terms of cooperation. As shown in the table, the overall mean was 4.75, indicating strongly agree or very high. All of the respondents rated strongly agreed with all the indicators on the following statements: People around me respect the teaching profession with 4.76; Teachers are well accepted by people in this area with 4.76; The teachers in our school cooperate with each other in line with their Professional goals with 4.77; Our school has a teaching staff to work with pleasure with 4.73; The cooperation of the teachers in our school makes me feel safe with 4.74; and I think that the teacher I work with has Professional ethics with 4.74.

Based on the results, it can be said that teachers gain confidence and strength as a result of helping their coworkers with their job-related issues and being really polite to them. In addition, it can be said that strong teachers help the organization's social standing, go above and beyond the call of duty, work and cooperate professionally, adjust to new developments more quickly, and collaborate and assist the organization.

Table 6. *Organizational Commitment in Terms of Moral*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1. I feel devoted to my school.	4.69	Strongly Agree
2. I feel that I have to support my school.	4.73	Strongly Agree
3. I see myself as an employee of the school even when I'm out of school.	4.44	Agree
4. I feel that it is my responsibility to help my school succeed.	4.66	Strongly Agree
5. I get upset when people say bad things about my school.	4.51	Strongly Agree
Average	4.61	Strongly Agree

In terms of moral in organizational commitment, it may be perused in Table 6 that teachers have a very high organizational commitment in terms of moral, indicating strongly agree with a mean of 4.61.

Most of the respondents rated strongly agreed with all the indicators on the following statements; I feel devoted to my school; I feel that I have to support my school; I feel that it is my responsibility to help my school succeed; and I get upset when people say bad things about my school with 4.69, 4.73, 4.66, and 4.51 of mean scores, respectively. On the other hand, I see myself as an employee of the school even when I'm out of school and got a mean score of 4.44, indicating a verbal description of agree.

The results of this study showed that teachers had the most moral commitment. For the school organization, this is a beneficial condition. Because high moral commitment demonstrates that employees internalize their feeling of duty from school and hence embrace their institutions, as well as generate a sense of belongingness to their institutions.

Table 7. *Organizational Commitment in Terms of Alienative*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation	
1. I sometimes want to leave my school and never want to come back again.	2.25	Disagree	
2. I often feel and find myself taking revenge on my school.	1.56	Disagree	PAGE
3. I feel angry when I think of my school.	1.88	Disagree	45
4. I feel trapped.	2.15	Disagree	
14. No matter what I do at my school, the school remains unchanged.	2.82	Neutral	
Average	2.13	Disagree	

Meanwhile, in Table 7, teachers overall disagree with the statements about organizational commitment in terms of alienative, indicating a mean of 2.13.

Most of the respondents rated disagreed with all the indicators on the following statements: I sometimes want to leave my school and never want to come back again with 2.25; I often feel and find myself taking revenge on my school with 1.56; I feel angry when I think of my school with 1.88; and I feel trapped with 2.15. On the contrary, No matter what I do at my school, the school remains unchanged and got a verbal description of neutral with 2.82 mean score.

Table 8. *Organizational Commitment in Terms of Calculative*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1. I try my best if my contributions to the school are seen and appreciated.	2.93	Neutral
4. I feel more comfortable with my work that I integrate too much when I see the rewards of my work.	4.16	Agree
7. The thought of getting more individual rewards from my school even motivates me.	3.54	Agree
10 I make an effort to the extent that I get rewarded in my school.	3.33	Neutral
13. I support my school as much as it supports me.	4.61	Strongly Agree
Average	3.72	Agree

Table 8 presents the organizational commitment in terms of calculative. As shown in the table, the overall mean was 3.72, indicating agree or high.

The results reveal that teachers have a moderate level of calculative commitment. The reasons for their calculative commitment to their school may be that they feel more comfortable with their work, and the support they are getting from the institutions.

Table 9. *Professional Commitment in Terms of Professional Pleasure*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1. I enjoy doing my job.	3.85	Agree
2. If I had the opportunity, I would change my job.	2.98	Agree
3. I enjoy raising children.	3.78	Agree
4. I enjoy talking about my job.	3.67	Agree
5. I like taking care of children.	3.79	Agree
6. I love my job.	4.31	Agree
Average	3.73	Agree

The teachers agreed with their professional commitment in terms of professional pleasure as shown by the mean scores of 3.73. All of the respondents rated agreed with all the indicators on the following statements in professional pleasure: I enjoy doing my job; If I had the opportunity, I would change my job; I enjoy raising children; I enjoy talking about my job; I like taking care of children; and I love my job with 3.85, 2.98, 3.78, 3.67, 3.79, and 4.31 of mean scores, respectively.

Table 10. *Professional Commitment in Terms of Social Gain*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
7. I feel safe in my job.	4.18	Agree
8. I feel my professional personal rights to be sufficient.	3.71	Agree
9. I think that my job gives me respect in society.	4.76	Strongly Agree
10. I have a job with comfortable working conditions.	3.69	Agree
11. I have enough rest in my job.	2.26	Disagree
Average	3.72	Agree

The teachers agreed with their professional commitment in terms of social gain, and professional career as shown by the mean score of 3.72. All of the respondents rated agreed with all the indicators of social gain: I feel safe in my job; I feel my professional personal rights to be sufficient; I think that my job gives me respect in society; I have a job with comfortable working conditions; and I have enough rest in my job with 4.18, 3.71, 4.76, 3.69, and 2.26 of mean scores, respectively.

The data show that teachers perceived their social gain levels to be high, signifying that their social status and working conditions were excellent. In addition, it was determined that instructors had a high perception of their professional commitment. Based on the scale's items, it can be concluded that teachers adore and accept their profession, follow professional developments, contribute to the development of their profession, and are proud to be in the profession. On the basis of the scale's items, it can be concluded that teachers like and embrace their profession, follow professional developments, and contribute to the development of their profession.

Table 11. *Professional Commitment in Terms of Professional Career*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1. I spent most of my time working at my job.	4.47	Agree
2. I believe that I should focus on my job.	4.43	Agree
3. I have career plans related to my job.	3.70	Agree
Average	4.20	Agree

The teachers all agreed with their professional commitment in terms of professional career as shown by the mean scores of 4.20. All of the respondents rated agreed on all the indicators in professional career: I spent most of my time working at my job with 4.47; I believe that I should focus on my job with 4.43, and I have career plans related to my job with 3.70.

Table 12. *Organizational Behaviors in Terms of Cooperation*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1. I do not tend to make “Mountains out of molehills.	3.81	Agree
2. I do not consume a lot of time complaining about trivial matters.	3.50	Agree
3. I never find fault with what the organization is doing.	4.24	Agree
4. I always focus on the positive side rather than the negative side.	4.68	Agree
5. I am not the classic “squeaky wheel” that always needs greasing.	3.98	Agree
6. I am always ready to lend a helping hand to those around me.	4.28	Agree
7. I help orient new people even though it is not required.	3.59	Agree
8. I help others who have heavy workloads.	3.64	Agree
Average	3.96	Agree

The teachers agreed with their organizational behaviors in terms of cooperation as shown by the mean scores of 3.96. All of the respondents rated agreed on all the indicators in cooperation: I do not tend to make “Mountains out of molehills with 3.81; I do not consume a lot of time complaining about trivial matters with 3.50; I never find fault with what the organization is doing with 4.24; I always focus on the positive side rather than the negative side with 4.68; I am not the classic “squeaky wheel” that always needs greasing with 3.98; I am always ready to lend a helping hand to those around me with 4.28; I help orient new people even though it is not required with 3.59; and I help others who have heavy workloads with 3.64.

Teachers demonstrate a strong inclination towards cooperation, emphasizing the positive aspects over the negative ones, reflecting an optimistic outlook. This positive perception of cooperation suggests that teachers are motivated and driven to fulfill their responsibilities with diligence and excellence. Their optimistic attitude towards collaboration indicates a proactive approach in fostering supportive and constructive relationships within their professional environment. By prioritizing positivity in cooperation, teachers contribute positively to the overall atmosphere and effectiveness of educational settings. This inclination towards emphasizing positivity underscores their commitment to maintaining a conducive and encouraging atmosphere for teaching and learning.

Table 13. *Organizational Behaviors in Terms of Kindness*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
9. I help others who have been absent.	4.08	Agree
10. I am willing to help others who have work-related Problems	4.19	Agree

11. I am one of the most conscientious employees.	3.53	Agree
12. I believe in giving an honest day's work for an honest day's pay.	4.19	Agree
Average	4.00	Agree

The teachers agreed with their organizational behaviors in terms of kindness as shown by the mean scores of 4.00. All of the respondents rated agreed on all the indicators in kindness: I help others who have been absent with 4.08; I am willing to help others who have work-related problems with 4.19; I am one of the most conscientious employees with 3.53; and I believe in giving an honest day's work for an honest day's pay with 4.19.

Teachers have high perceptions of kindness which includes helping other employees with school-related tasks and problems. In other words, teachers view themselves as helpful, accountable, and productive in school-related work. In addition, teachers believe that students demonstrate exemplary organizational citizenship. In other words, teachers believe that their duties and behaviors align with the school's objectives and requirements.

Table 14. *Organizational Behaviors in Terms of Conscientiousness*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
13. I obey company rules and regulations even when no one is watching.	4.26	Agree
14. I do not take extra breaks.	3.43	Neutral
15. My attendance at work is above the norm.	3.61	Agree
16. I do not abuse the rights of others.	4.74	Strongly Agree
Average	4.01	Agree

The teachers agreed with their organizational behaviors in terms of conscientiousness as shown by the mean scores of 4.00. All of the respondents rated agreed on all the indicators in conscientiousness: I obey company rules and regulations even when no one is watching with 4.26; I do not take extra breaks with 3.43; My attendance at work is above the norm with 3.61; and I do not abuse the rights of others with 4.74. Teachers have a very high perception of conscientiousness, which indicates that they are willing to go above and beyond what is expected of them.

Table 15. *Organizational Behaviors in Terms of Civil Virtue*

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
17. I consider the impact of my actions on coworkers.	4.67	Strongly Agree
18. I try to avoid creating problems for co-workers.	4.74	Strongly Agree
19. I take steps to try to prevent problems with other	4.64	Strongly Agree

workers.

20. I am mindful of how my behavior affects other people's jobs.	4.67	Strongly Agree
Average	4.68	Strongly Agree

The teachers strongly agreed with their organizational behaviors in terms of civil virtue as shown by the mean scores of 4.68. All of the respondents rated strongly agreed on all the indicators in civil virtue: I consider the impact of my actions on coworkers with 4.67; I try to avoid creating problems for co-workers with 4.74; I take steps to try to prevent problems with other workers with 4.64; and I am mindful of how my behavior affects other people's jobs with 4.67.

Teachers have high perceptions of civil virtue, which includes gathering information about what is occurring in their schools and partaking in the political life of their schools as responsible, and constructive individual.

Table 16. *Regression Analysis of Empowerment on Organizational Behaviors*

Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	0.943	0.36		2.62	0.01
Teacher empowerment	0.234	0.061	0.264	3.86	0.000
Organizational commitment	0.076	0.076	0.078	1.005	0.317
Professional commitment	0.457	0.054	0.65	8.41	0.000
r-square = .521					
f-value = 39.087					
p-value = .000					
alpha = .05					

Regression analysis was conducted to examine the independent constructs as the influence of empowerment with the dependent variable: teachers' organizational behaviors.

Results of the regression analysis in Table 16 reveal that teacher empowerment, organizational commitment, and professional commitment have Beta coefficients of 0.264, 0.078, and 0.65 respectively with a p-value, which does not exceed the 0.05 alpha. Data denotes an F value of 39.087 with a significant value of 0.000 is lower than the alpha 0.05, which means that the predictor variable collectively accounts for a statistically significant proportion of the variance in the criterion variable of teachers' organizational behaviors.

Since the associated probability does not exceed .05 alpha, it is, therefore, safe to conclude that empowerment has a significant influence on teachers' organizational behaviors. Hence, the decision is to reject the null hypothesis, which states that empowerment has no significant influence on teachers' organizational behaviors.

DISCUSSION

This section summarizes and illustrates the results that the researchers have gathered from the study.

1. Empowerment

The results show that teachers have a very high level of trust in their schools which according to Hidiruglo (2017), it signifies that employees who perceive themselves as having high levels of empowerment are more motivated to work toward corporate goals and believe that doing so will help them meet their own needs.

In this outcome, it is evident that teachers perceive their institutions as supportive of their professional development. This finding aligns with Kiral (2020) research, which indicates that empowering teachers involves granting them greater autonomy, involving them in decision-making processes, fostering a sense of community within classrooms, encouraging ongoing professional and personal growth, and integrating teachers' unique circumstances.

The research suggests that when an employee feels appreciated and experiences a sense of achievement, there is a higher likelihood of enhancing their creativity and critical thinking abilities (Agyemang & Ofei, 2018). Empowering workers by granting them greater autonomy in their roles allows them to respond quickly to changes and devise solutions to meet customer needs (Appelbaum et al., 2018).

2. Organizational Behavior

According to Ergün (2017), teachers exhibit moderate levels of moral commitment, whereas their calculative and alienative commitments are below the moderate threshold. Similarly, Ziblim and Ertürk, (2022) categorized teachers' commitment into three levels: high for moral commitment, and lower levels for calculative and alienative commitments.

The results of this study revealed that teachers' organizational commitment in terms of alienative commitment was the lowest average and least preferred type of commitment in organizations. This was due to compulsory commitment, where a person does not feel any commitment to the organization and is forced to remain in the organization. In this sense, it might be said that teachers support their institutions out of a sense of duty rather than obligation. A study by Yavuzkiç (2022) found that teachers had extremely high levels of moral and calculative commitment while having extremely low levels of alienative commitment.

The findings suggest that teachers expressed satisfaction and value for their jobs. Job satisfaction refers to the state of being content with one's work and desired outcomes (Hoy & Tarter, 2011, as cited in Hidoruglo, 2017). Consistent with this data, teachers indicated a considerable degree of professional contentment or satisfaction with their profession.

The findings of this study align with Tindowen (2019), which similarly concluded that teachers exhibit high levels of empowerment. This consistency underscores a broader pattern of teacher empowerment across various contexts, suggesting a robust trend in the profession. High levels of empowerment among teachers reflect positive organizational dynamics, with teachers feeling valued, efficacious, and influential within their educational environments. Such findings not only validate the importance of empowerment in enhancing teachers' professional experiences but also highlight its role in fostering a conducive and supportive work environment. This agreement between studies strengthens the understanding of empowerment's impact on teachers' attitudes, behaviors, and overall job satisfaction, emphasizing its significance in educational settings.

This indicates that teachers allocated time and attention to their roles and responsibilities. Research has shown that levels of professional commitment among teachers can vary. For instance, Ergen (2017) and Tindowen (2019) observed high levels of professional commitment, Alkhadher and Menge (2020) reported lower levels. The dedication of teachers to their profession is considered a critical factor in the success of education and schools. Decreased professional commitment can also impact school effectiveness by reducing teachers' professional performance or, in severe cases, leading to attrition from their positions (Chaurasia et al., 2020).

The findings mirrored those of previous research indicating that teachers' organizational behaviors tend to be notably strong (Çevik & Can, 2020). Given the significance of organizational citizenship behavior, existing literature underscores its promotion within organizations due to its positive impact on profitability and overall organizational performance (Nawaser et al., 2018). Furthermore, it is noteworthy that involving employees in routine decision-making processes correlates positively with their motivation to engage in citizenship behaviors and enhances overall performance (Khoshnamoghdam, 2017). In summary, the results underscore positive organizational behaviors exhibited by the respondents.

3. Regression Analysis of Empowerment on Organizational Behaviors

Positive organizational behaviors are influenced by teacher empowerment. This circumstance runs concurrently with previous investigations in the literature. (Tindowen, 2019). The results also indicate that the empowerment of the faculty members affected their organizational citizenship behavior, which is consistent with Tindowen's (2019) findings that empowerment affects organizational citizenship behavior.

Furthermore, it suggests that teachers will display organizational behaviors to a greater extent the more empowered they are which is similar to the findings of Posadas et al. (2021).

Also, according to LiMon (2022) organizational behaviors and teachers' organizational commitment have a favorable and significant relationship. Teacher education institutions should support efforts to further enhance the empowerment of their faculty members, as this will correlate to their display of organizational behavior for the benefit of students and the college/university. They should treat their teachers and personnel with transparency and care (Garcia & Subia, 2019).

Lastly, according to Hıdıroğlu & Tanrıöğen (2022), organizational commitment, professional commitment, and organizational citizenship are related. He determined that professional commitment and organizational commitment revealed the relative importance of the predictive variables associated with organizational behaviors. According to the research, schools should take steps to increase teachers' professional and organizational commitments, as well as their moral commitment, which is one of the organizational commitment categories.

4. Implications Drawn from the Findings of the Study

1. The research suggests that teachers who experience empowerment demonstrate positive organizational behaviors within schools. This empowerment stems from feelings of respect, access to professional development opportunities, effectiveness in the classroom, and the ability to influence students and school dynamics. However, they often lack sufficient involvement in institutional decision-making processes. Teachers exhibit positive organizational behaviors such as strong organizational attachment, high work engagement, and positive relationships with administrators.
2. School administrators play a critical role in empowering teachers by effectively utilizing their authority and resources. When teachers feel empowered, they are more inclined to engage in extra-role behaviors. Therefore, administrators should enhance their management and leadership skills to foster empowerment. Schools can benefit from implementing a range of empowerment practices to enhance teachers' professional and moral commitment, such as conducting needs assessments, implementing various initiatives, and offering training.
3. Studies consistently demonstrate that empowerment impacts organizational behaviors. Consequently, school leaders focused on cultivating teachers' organizational behaviors should prioritize empowerment through diverse strategies, policies, and approaches. Empowerment initiatives should aim to enhance teachers' relationships, communication, problem-solving abilities, attitudes, and professional values.

Conclusions

In light of the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The teachers demonstrated empowerment through their positive perceptions of personal and professional development, indicating a belief in their capacity to manage challenges independently.
2. Teachers exhibited exceptionally high organizational commitment, particularly in terms of moral commitment, reflecting a strong sense of dedication to their profession. Their positive views towards professional commitment suggest a high level of satisfaction in their work. Additionally, teachers consistently displayed various dimensions of organizational citizenship behavior, with acts of kindness being less frequent compared to other behaviors. Overall, teachers exhibited strong organizational behaviors beyond their formal role requirements within school settings.
3. Empowerment significantly influenced teachers' organizational citizenship behavior, highlighting the impact of feeling empowered on their discretionary actions within the organizational context.
4. School administrators play a crucial role in empowering teachers, emphasizing the importance of their involvement in fostering a supportive environment for teacher empowerment.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. To enhance teachers' perceptions of empowerment, particularly in the aspect of self-determination, it is suggested to involve them in decision-making processes related to their work and allow them greater autonomy in performing their duties. Additionally, a qualitative investigation could be conducted to explore how empowerment influences teachers' organizational behavior.
2. To promote increased organizational citizenship behaviors among teachers, policymakers and school administrators should prioritize initiatives that empower teachers, with a specific focus on granting autonomy. It is recommended that all education administrators create an environment that supports teachers in making independent decisions regarding matters that affect them.
3. An extension of this study could involve further exploration of significant teacher and school-related factors predicted by dimensions of teacher empowerment. This expanded research could encompass areas such as teachers' job satisfaction, faculty efficiency, work values, leadership, spirituality, religiosity, and other critical factors.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher rigorously adhered to established research protocols to uphold ethical standards throughout the study, prioritizing the protection of all individuals and institutions involved. This commitment involved obtaining informed consent from participants, ensuring confidentiality and anonymity of sensitive information, and minimizing potential risks or harm associated with the research process. Ethical considerations were meticulously integrated into all phases of the study, from design and data collection to analysis and dissemination of findings. The researcher took proactive measures to safeguard the rights, welfare, and privacy of participants and institutions, in accordance with applicable guidelines and regulations. By upholding ethical principles, the researcher aimed to foster trust, integrity, and accountability in the research endeavor, maintaining the ethical integrity of the study while upholding professional standards and responsibilities.

Acknowledgments

This research project owes its success to the invaluable contributions of generous individuals who dedicated their time and efforts to support its realization. Their support was essential in navigating challenges and achieving milestones throughout the study. Special thanks are extended to friends and classmates whose companionship and encouragement provided solace during challenging times, fostering happiness and comfort.

Above all, gratitude is expressed to our Almighty God, whose unconditional love and boundless forgiveness have provided strength, patience, and countless blessings. The researchers attribute their guidance, provision of knowledge, and wisdom to the divine, enabling them to navigate each task with confidence and resilience. Every challenge encountered has served to shape them into better, stronger individuals, for which they are deeply thankful and humbled by the experience.

REFERENCES

- Agyemang, C. B., & Ofei, S. B. (2018). Employee work engagement and organizational commitment: A Comparative study of private and public sector organizations in Ghana. *European Journal of Business and Innovation Research*, 1(4), 20-33.
- Alkhadher, O., Beehr, T., & Meng, L. (2020). Individualism-collectivism and nation as moderators of the job satisfaction- organisational citizenship behaviour relationship in the United States, China, and Kuwait. *Asian Journal of Social Psychology*
- Appelbaum, S. H., Karasek, R., Lapointe, F., & Quelch, K. (2018). Employee empowerment: factors affecting the consequent success or failure (Part II). *Industrial and commercial training*, 47(1), 23-30.

- Bhandari, P. (2020). What Is Quantitative Research?
- Çevik, A. & Can, N. (2020). Modular power resources of school administrators as a predictor of organizational citizenship and organizational cynicism behaviors of teachers. *Academia Eğitim Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 5(1), 13-30.
- Chaurasia, S. S., Kaul, N., Yadav, B. S., & Shukla, D. (2020). Open innovation for sustainability through creating shared value-role of knowledge management system, openness and organizational structure. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 24(10), 2491–2511. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jkm-04-2020-0319>
- Cheasakul, U. & Varma, P. (2018). The Influence of Passion and Empowerment on Organizational Citizenship Behavior of Teachers Mediated by Organizational Commitment. *Contaduría Administración*, 61, 422–440. Retrieved from <http://www.scielo.org.mx/pdf/cya/v61n3/0186-1042-cya-61-03-00422.pdf>
- Duncan, C., & Sankey, D. (2019). Two conflicting visions of education and their consilience. *Educational Philosophy and Theory*, 51(14), 1454–1464. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131857.2018.1557044>
- Ergen, B., & Kanadili S. (2017). The Effect of Self-Regulated Learning Strategies on Academic Achievement: A Meta-Analysis Study. *Eurasian Journal of Educational Research*, 17(69), 55–74. <https://doi.org/10.14689/ejer.2017.69.4>
- Ergün, K. (2017). Financial literacy among university students: A study in eight European countries. *International Journal of Consumer Studies (Print)*, 42(1), 2–15. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijcs.12408>
- Garcia, M. & Subia, G. (2019). High School Athletes: Their Motivation, Study Habits, Self-discipline, and Academic Performance. *International Journal of Physical Education, Sports and Health* 2019; 6(1): 86–90.
- Hidroğlu & Tanrıoğen (2022). The Mediating Role of Organizational and Professional Commitment in the Relationship between Teacher Empowerment and Organizational Citizenship Behaviors.
- Hidiruglo N. (2017). The effect of structural and Psychological empowerment on teachers' motivation. *Kırıkkale University Journal of Social Sciences*, 7(2), 361-377.
- Imam, A. & Shafique, M. (2018). Impact of Employee Engagement in Retaining Employees Through Mediating Effect of Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment and Moderating Effect of Job Stress: A Corporate Banking Sector Study of Pakistan. *Journal of Applied Environmental and Biological Sciences*, 4(12), 1-15.
- Kabeer, N. (2019). Resources, agency, achievements: Reflections on the measurement of women's empowerment. *Development and Change*, 30(3), 435-464.
- Kıral, B. (2020). A case study regarding of the parental responsibilities to their children. *Eurasian Journal of Educational Research*, 20(85), 65–92. <https://doi.org/10.14689/ejer.2020.85.4>
- Khoshnammoghadam, F. (2017). The impact of organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) and organizational commitment on market-orientation of the banks (case study: Parsian bank branches in Tehran).
- LiMon, İ. (2022). Relationship between Empowering Leadership and Teachers' Job Performance: Organizational Commitment as Mediator. *Kuramsal Eğitim Bilim Dergisi*, 15(1), 16–41. <https://doi.org/10.30831/akukeyg.945201>

- Mesbahi, M. (2017). Mediator Role of Social Capital and Organizational Commitment in the Relation of Service-Oriented Motivation and Organizational Citizenship Behavior. *World Scientific News*, 64, 54-68.
- Nawaser, K., Ahmadi, M., Ahmadi, Y., & Dorostkar, M. (2018). Organizational citizenship behavior and bank profitability: Examining relationships in an Iranian Bank.
- Özkan Hidiroğlu, Y., & Tanrıöğen, A. (2020). Development of Teachers' Empowerment Scale: A Validity and Reliability Study. *International Journal of Assessment Tools in Education*, 7(4), 753-772. <https://doi.org/10.21449/ijate.693398>
- Posadas, K. F., Osabel, A. C., Cruz, M. T. a. D., Villafior, M. R. D., Suarez, N. C., Flores, J. T., Mañas, J. L., Yago, C. S., & Adrales, D. M. (2021). Employability of teacher education graduates of Nueva Ecija university of science and technology, San Isidro campus. *International Journal of Applied Research (Delhi)*, 7(6), 159–164. <https://doi.org/10.22271/allresearch.2021.v7.i6c.8650>
- Podsakoff, P. M., MacKenzie, S. B., Moorman, R. H., & Fetter, R. (1990). Transformational leader behaviors and their effects on followers' trust in leader, satisfaction, and organizational citizenship behaviors. *The Leadership Quarterly/the Leadership Quarterly*, 1(2), 107–142. [https://doi.org/10.1016/1048-9843\(90\)90009-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/1048-9843(90)90009-7)
- Polat, S. (2019). Organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) display levels of the teachers at secondary schools according to the perceptions of the school administrators. *Procedia: Social & Behavioral Sciences*, 1(1), 1591–1596. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2009.01.280>
- Tindowen, D. J. (2019). Influence of empowerment on teachers' organizational behaviours. *European Journal of Educational Research*, 8(2), 617-631. <https://doi.org/10.12973/eu-jer.8.2.617>.
- Ziblim, L., & Ertürk, A. (2022). The organizational power applied by school principals and its effect on teachers' perception of power distance. *Participatory Educational Research*, 9(5), 26–42. <https://doi.org/10.17275/per.22.102.9.5>